

Molecular Docking Studies for Reducing Inflammation in Inflammatory Breast Cancer Patients

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I. Abstract

Oxidoreductases are enzymes that catalyze the oxidation of one molecule to another using NAD⁺ and NADP as co-factors. In this study, molecular docking is done for the human Toll-like receptor 4 (Uniprot ID: O00206). Human Toll-like receptor 4 (PDB ID: 3FXI) was selected as target crystal structure based on its specific criteria (resolution 3.10 Å, R_{free} value 0.281, Ramachandran outliers value greater than 2.8%). The receptor was optimized using Chimera and CHem3D. Then it was prepared with AutoDock. Its active site was determined using AutoDock grid tool. The co-crystallized ligand was prepared using open babel. Molecular docking was done for the receptor, two ligands modified from the original co-crystallized ligand, and other 98 ligands obtained from zinc15 database through searching by the smiles of the original ligand and selecting the available structures for sale. The best results were obtained based on their binding configuration and binding affinity using Autodock Vina. Also, the receptor-ligand interactions of the top ligands were visualized.

Index Terms- human Toll-like receptor 4; Inflammatory Breast cancer; protein-ligand docking; virtual screening, binding site prediction

II. Introduction

Breast cancer ranks as a leading cause of death in women worldwide and it represents 11.9% of all cancer world-wide [1]. Inflammatory breast cancer (IBC) is an aggressive and fatal form of breast cancer that is more prominent among young women and is characterized by a high number of axillary lymph node metastases at the time of presentation, poor prognosis, and low survival rate [2-6]. Toll-like receptors (TLRs) are considered a link between innate (non-specific) and adaptive (specific) immunity and TLRs contribute to the immune system's capacity to efficiently combat pathogens. This is done by means of the induction of signaling cascades resulting in the induction of type I interferons (IFNs) and other cytokines. The result of this process leads to an inflammatory response and activates the adaptive immune system. TLRs also enable immune cells to discriminate between self and nonself antigens [7]. As molecular sensors, TLRs detect pathogen-derived products and trigger protective responses. These responses include the secretion of cytokines that increase the resistance of infected cells as well as the release of chemokines that recruit immune cells to dead cells, thus limiting microbe spreading. Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4) has been implicated in the development of several types of cancer [8]. In this study, we explored the impact of TLR4 on inflammatory breast cancer.

III. Methodology

1. Molecular optimization of the crystallographic proteins

The Crystal structure of the human TLR4 protein (PDB ID: 3FXI) has been chosen for the study after scanning multiple literature to select the most related target to inflammation that could be targeted for reducing breast cancer inflammations [9]. The PDB structure was accessible through <https://www.rcsb.org/pdb> [10]. By MOE [11], water molecules and ions were deleted and hydrogens were added. By CHem3D [12], amino acids with missing atoms were optimized. We only selected the good quality chains (A and C) to work on for reducing the computational resources needed for molecular docking.

Fig. 1. Crystal structure of the human TLR4-human MD-2-E.coli LPS Ra complex.

Fig. 2. 3FXI Multipercentile validation on PDB

Mol	Chain	Length	Quality of chain
1	A	605	 2% 68% 26% 5%
1	B	605	 4% 68% 25% 5%
2	C	142	 58% 34% 7%
2	D	142	 61% 31% 7%

Fig. 3. 3FXI Quality of Chains on PDB

2. *Molecular optimization of the co-crystallized ligand*

Optimization of ligand chemical structure was using Chem3D software by first adjusting the bond order, add charges, and then add hydrogens. Energy minimization was done by MM2 energy minimization from Chem3D . Bond order and charges before adding hydrogens were adjusted.

3. *Visualization of receptor binding site and analysis of ligand-receptor interactions*

Using Chimera and RCSB [13], visualization of the receptor binding site, the original (co-crystallized) ligand, and the main ligand-receptor interaction were carefully checked.

4. *Molecular Docking*

The original ligand was used for getting two other ligands by performing modifications and replacements to the functional groups. The simles description of the original ligand was used for obtaining the available drugs for sale that have a similar composition as the ligand. The docking script uses all the prepared ligands (The co-crystallized ligands as well as the two modified ligands and the other 98 ligands obtained from Zinc15 database [14]) to find and select the best poses with the lowest energy by trying ten different poses for each ligand. The 2D diagrams of the receptor ligand interaction for the top five ligands were obtained by Discovery studio. For target-ligand docking analysis. Autodock Vina was used [15-16]. First, based on the already present co-crystallized ligand in the pdb file, the active site was defined with grid box parameters and coordinate of origin (x, y and z). This gives enough space to enhance ligand rotation and translation. The spacing between grid points was maintained at 1 angstrom. All ligands were docked to the active site of the receptor. Throughout this study, the rotatable bonds of the ligands were set to be free, however the protein molecule was treated as rigid structure. A total of ten docking runs were performed for each ligand with the number of modes set to 10 so as to achieve more accurate and reliable results. The five best results obtained based on the binding configuration and binding affinity were chosen for further analysis [17].

Ligand	Docking Score	Ligand	Docking Score	Ligand	Docking Score	Ligand	Docking Score
zinc_lig65	-1.9	zinc_lig9	6.5	zinc_lig50	13.9	zinc_lig90	34
zinc_lig95	-1.7	zinc_lig27	6.7	zinc_lig25	14.1	zinc_lig77	34.4
co-lig	0.2	zinc_lig73	6.7	zinc_lig5	14.7	zinc_lig67	35
lig-1	0.3	lig-2	6.8	zinc_lig1	15.5	zinc_lig45	36.5
zinc_lig85	0.9	zinc_lig33	7.8	zinc_lig59	15.7	zinc_lig35	37.7
zinc_lig12	1	zinc_lig30	8	zinc_lig10	16	zinc_lig41	38.1
zinc_lig54	1.6	zinc_lig23	8.2	zinc_lig21	16.1	zinc_lig52	38.1
zinc_lig18	1.8	zinc_lig14	8.6	zinc_lig46	16.1	zinc_lig89	38.2
zinc_lig68	1.9	zinc_lig29	8.6	zinc_lig34	16.2	zinc_lig79	39
zinc_lig71	1.9	zinc_lig4	8.8	zinc_lig61	16.3	zinc_lig91	40
zinc_lig55	2	zinc_lig15	9	zinc_lig56	16.8	zinc_lig75	43.1
zinc_lig37	2.1	zinc_lig3	9.1	zinc_lig98	17	zinc_lig94	47.6
zinc_lig80	2.1	zinc_lig8	9.1	zinc_lig16	17.1	zinc_lig40	47.7
zinc_lig19	2.5	zinc_lig42	9.3	zinc_lig57	17.1	zinc_lig49	54.5
zinc_lig72	2.5	zinc_lig28	9.7	zinc_lig13	17.9	zinc_lig76	54.5
zinc_lig38	2.7	zinc_lig62	9.7	zinc_lig24	19.1	zinc_lig82	57.3
zinc_lig74	2.7	zinc_lig53	10.2	zinc_lig99	21.5	zinc_lig70	57.9
zinc_lig31	3	zinc_lig7	10.3	zinc_lig84	25	zinc_lig97	58.1
zinc_lig66	3.2	zinc_lig63	10.6	zinc_lig48	25.8	zinc_lig100	60.9
zinc_lig86	3.4	zinc_lig17	11.4	zinc_lig36	26	zinc_lig81	63.6
zinc_lig69	4	zinc_lig26	12.6	zinc_lig20	27.1	zinc_lig2	67.6
zinc_lig32	4.1	zinc_lig47	12.9	zinc_lig58	28.5	zinc_lig96	70.3
zinc_lig39	4.4	zinc_lig22	13	zinc_lig44	30.8	zinc_lig6	71.3
zinc_lig11	4.9	zinc_lig60	13.1	zinc_lig51	31.8	zinc_lig43	87.9
zinc_lig87	6.2	zinc_lig83	13.5	zinc_lig93	33.8	zinc_lig88	88.1

Table 1:Ligands Docking scores

IV. Results and Discussion

1. Validation of Protein Structure

The human Toll-like receptor 4 (PDB ID: 3FXI) was evaluated based on multiple criteria (resolution 3.10Å, Rfree value 0.281, Ramachandran outliers value greater than 2.8%). The Ramachandran plot shows that 90.7% (1337/1474) of all residues were in favored (98%) regions and 99.0% (1459/1474) of all residues were in allowed (>99.8%) regions [19].

Fig. 4. Ramachandran plot of the human TLR4-human

2. Molecular Modelling

Protein and ligand were prepared using Chimera and Chem 3D software. Figures 5-7 shows the compounds after adjusting the bond order, adding hydrogens (hidden the nonpolar hydrogen), and energy minimization.

Fig. 5. Co-crystallized Ligand

Fig. 6. Modified ligand (lig-1)

Fig. 7. Modified ligand (lig-2)

3. Visualization of receptor binding site and analysis of ligand-receptor interactions

the receptor binding site, the original (co-crystallized) ligand, and the main ligand-receptor interaction are shown in Figure 8-9.

Fig. 8. Crystal structure of the human TLR4-human MD-2-E.coli LPS Ra complex
Target Focus

Fig. 9. Crystal structure of the human TLR4-human MD-2-E.coli LPS Ra complex
Target Surrounding Focus

4. Molecular Docking

Ligand-receptor interactions of the original ligand and the top docked ligands are shown in Figures 10-17.

Fig. 10. Co-crystallized Ligand Interactions

Fig. 11. Lig-1 Synthesized Interactions

Fig. 12. Lig65 Interactions

Fig. 13. Lig95 Interactions

Fig. 14. Co-crystallized Ligand Interactions

Fig. 15. Lig-1 Synthesized Interactions

Fig. 16. Lig-2 Synthesized Interactions

Fig. 17. Lig95 Interactions

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